

SUPPORTIVE STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE WRITING SKILL

Gulmira Juraboyeva¹, Dinara Saydullayeva Lutfulla qizi²

¹ Student of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

gulmirajuraboyeva@gmail.com,

² Student of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the strategies based on improving writing skill. Both teachers and students should stick to the rules in order to attain signed destination.

Introduction

Writing warm-ups are great to help students get their creative juices flowing. They are also helpful to encourage students to write down their thoughts. Using a writing warm-up like Power Writing or Free writing: (where students write without stopping or without worrying about spelling or grammar) their ideas can flow and they don't have to deal with writing paralysis.

Pre-writing

This is a critical step for helping struggling writers construct ideas. Using tools like brainstorming or Focus Storms, help students quickly get as many ideas as possible. The blank page can be daunting to a young writer who struggles with coming up with ideas. Brainstorming is a powerful tool to help writers flush out all the ideas and then a Focus Storm helps them to organize and fine-tune their ideas. This is also helpful because it is a visual for

students to see that they have lots of ideas. If students ever get stuck for ideas, they can refer back to their brainstorm and focus storm.

Disorganization and lack of structure

This was one of my biggest struggles as a young writer. I had lots of ideas, but I rarely put them together in a coherent fashion. Instead, my writing was a disorganized, jumbled mess. Many young writers struggle with this aspect of writing, and these scaffolding tips are a best practice when teaching young students. Whether it is a paragraph or an essay, these strategies help support struggling writers in elementary school.

Chunk assignments with graphic organizers

Many struggling writers do better with a visual. Breaking writing up into more manageable chunks (breaking a paragraph

into sentences) makes the task seem less daunting and more doable.

Teacher leads modeling and guided writing

Before having your students begin a writing assignment, show them models (either teacher created, or exemplar student examples from the past). Additionally, if you are having a student write a hook, model to the class, how you would write a hook. By thinking aloud, this demonstrates for the struggling writers how they can approach the same situation. This is a good time to encourage students to share their samples. Additionally, this helps spark ideas in students who might be stuck [1].

Mini writing lessons

Don't expect students to know how to write an engaging lead sentence, or use transitional phrases fluently. These are excellent mini-lessons to incorporate into your writing block. Take 10 - 15 minutes to teach and practice a writing strategy (like writing a lead sentence for an informative writing assignment). Once you teach the skill, have students immediately practice it in their writing. As you introduce more mini-writing lessons, don't forget to still touch on ones you have covered in the past.

Methods

Provide students with writing tools

Giving students a writing toolbox will give them a resource to get support with their writing. For instance, provide students with a list of transitional words and phrases for the writing they are tackling. Or give students a list of Dead Words that they should avoid using in their writing and a

list of alternative words to use instead. Giving students a resource to refer to while writing will help them overcome their writing challenges.

Results and Discussion

Disconnect from assignment

Sometimes the problem with struggling writers is that they just don't care about the assignment given. Either they can't connect to the assignment (they don't have any experience going to the beach, so how can we expect them to write a story about going to the beach), or there is no motivation with the writing purpose - another paragraph for the teacher, who cares! These two scaffolding tools can help to increase motivation and create an authentic writing experience.

Student choice

Give students choice with what they write about. Even a little choice goes a long way with student writing. When students feel invested in a topic they will have more to say, thus more to write.

Sense of purpose

Except for those teacher-pleasers and highly intrinsically motivated students, there is little drive and motivation to do their best work when students are simply writing for a teacher to grade. Thus it is important to create an authentic writing situation for students. Have them write a blog post to share with the entire third grade, or have them create a persuasive travel brochure. When there is a greater purpose to their writing, even struggling writers invest more in the assignment [2].

Sometimes students struggle in more than one area or they need more individualized support.

Conference with students individually and in small groups

Since students are so different with their writing abilities and their struggles, it is important to find a time to meet with students in small groups or individually to identify each students' strengths and weaknesses. Knowing which areas to target for each writer will allow you to scaffold and support each student in the area in which they could benefit the most.

My goal as a writing teacher is to help all my students feel successful with writing. I scaffold writing instruction to support all my struggling writers from the kids who struggle with coming up with ideas, to the writers who need support.

State and national standards, as well as the research we have on writing and its development, pinpoint six critical goals for all of our students when it comes to developing their identities as writers. a) Facility With the Writing Process and Writing Contexts Basic components of the writing process include prewriting, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing. Skilled writers use these parts of the process recursively and thoughtfully—not as a simple sequence of events! By the end of the elementary grades, our students need to be engaging successfully in each aspect of the writing process. The research is clear: students who know and use the writing process well become stronger writers.

As students become immersed in the writing process and develop “know how,” they develop powerful academic language

that will be invaluable as they continue to develop as writers in middle and high school—and beyond. By the end of the elementary grades, our students should have a solid foundation in the language used in discourse about writing. This foundation of writing skills for elementary students should be developed across listening, speaking, reading, and writing. We know that students who can use academic language effectively are more likely to succeed in and out of school. Learning how to choose words carefully when writing to maximize communicating with your reader, and developing word learning strategies, will set our students on the path to expand and deepen their vocabulary and their effective use of language when writing. d) Writing to Comprehend and Learn: Reading and writing in the elementary classroom are two of the primary cornerstones for building content learning across the curriculum. Until recently, writing effectively to inform or persuade after close reading of source texts was not a common expectation in the elementary grades. Many state and national standards now require fourth and fifth graders to write logical and compelling informative or persuasive essays based on close reading of source text—referring to text that can be read to obtain facts, definitions, details, quotations, ideas, or other information.

Conclusion

Additional writing strategies for elementary school students to enhance learning include writing a summary, writing to apply content learned, using writing to connect content to one's personal life, and defending a particular point of view about what has been read.

Creative teachers find many meaningful ways to integrate reading and writing, and research shows integrating the two leads to improvements in each. Teachers and researchers have shown that even early elementary grade students can learn how to write based on what they have learned by reading and discussion! e) Competence and Fluency With Writing Conventions, Sentence Construction, Digital Tools,

Handwriting, Spelling, and Keyboarding Skilled writers rarely have to think about handwriting, keyboarding, or spelling. Explicit development of each of these skills is critical in the elementary grades. Further, by the end of the elementary grades our students should have a sound foundation in use of writing conventions, creating effective sentences, and use of digital tools [4].

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